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WATER ASSET CONDITION MONITORING CLASSIFICATION: INVESTIGATING THE USE OF MACHINE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT: Condition monitoring systems for drinking water systems have recently provided positive and effective changes in how we prioritize management of our underground infrastructure. They provide means to strategically deal with the 13,200 additional miles of critical water infrastructure that need replacement in the U.S. in the next 15 to 20 years. And are becoming the innovative solutions that large municipalities are adopting to save millions of dollars from water loss and emergency repairs.

This paper classifies the main condition monitoring technologies for drinking water assets from the results of a recent literature review, which has been conducted as part of a national research project in the U.S. In this study, the areas related to condition monitoring were broadly classified into equipment-based technologies, data-driven methods and supporting or related topics. A special exploratory review on the use of machine learning algorithms is investigated to assess how researchers employ these models as part of, or in conjunction with, condition monitoring technologies. The insights identified from the literature search serve to draw conclusions on current research needs for emerging technologies and for the uses of machine learning in this field.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the adoption of automatic meter reading (AMR) systems by drinking water utilities in the early 2000s (made possible by advanced metering infrastructures - AMI); there have been a surge of positive changes and steps forward in the field of condition monitoring of critical assets. In recent years, some critical drinking water assets are being retrofitted with emerging structural monitoring technologies that use specially designed equipment or data driven algorithms to determine the current condition of assets or predict its remaining useful life (RUL).

Usually, utility assets related to drinking water systems that require some level of condition monitoring include dams, reservoirs, water filtration systems, water storage tanks, pumping stations, valves, and pipelines. Most of the cases mentioned before are above-ground assets that can be regularly inspected, or continuously monitored, in an almost automatic approach. For example, dams have been traditionally monitored continuously by using geotechnical instrumentation including inclinometers and extensometers for soil displacement, piezometers for groundwater levels and pore pressures, pressure cells for determining pressures applied to earth dams, concrete embedded or rebar soldered strain gauges for measuring stresses, motion accelerographs for detecting dam wall tilt motions, and survey points for monitoring overall dam wall positioning. Also, drones have recently been used as an adapted new technology for periodical dam monitoring. However, this automatic and continuous multi-

sensor monitoring approach is only possible because these assets have been equipped with sensors during construction, and because they are located above ground which makes them relatively easier to access.

On the contrary, most of the critical underground assets on our drinking water systems are usually not pre-equipped with monitoring sensors, and of course are not easily accessible since they are buried. Often, underground drinking water assets are in saturated easements and below highly congested areas, which makes it even more difficult to assess their condition. Additionally, the expenses associated with excavating several locations for a close-up inspection may be cost prohibiting. Thus, monitoring programs can help find which specific assets are degrading quicker. However, in general, the predicting result of monitoring is considered a time consuming and less rewarding task (Najafi et al. 2021).

Since the average age of the drinking water infrastructure in the USA is at least 45 years (EPA 2002), and because the annual rate of replacement for critical infrastructure is increasing from approximately 1.4% to 2% in the next 15 to 20 years (EPA 2002), which represents an additional 13,200 miles of pipelines to be replaced (based on ASCE (2021)); it is imperative to increase the close monitoring of these critical assets, to make better renewal or replacement decisions. Currently, the infrastructure in the USA, and possibly in the rest of the world, is vulnerable to catastrophic failures (Najafi et al. 2021). Unfortunately, when this essential infrastructure fails it threatens people's health, peace of mind, and the environment (EPA 2021), which results in costly, disruptive, and reactive construction activities (Najafi et al. 2021).

The highest levels of condition monitoring are often employed for large diameter transmission and distribution lines, which are essential components of any drinking water system, as indicated by EPA (2002). The pipe materials often associated with these assets include prestressed concrete cylinder pipes (PCCP) (AWWA C301), cast iron pipes (ASA A21.4); and to a lesser extent ductile iron pipes (AWWA C150 and C151) and steel pipes (AWWA C200). A definitive list of assets to closely monitor usually depends on a multilayered strategy, involving accurate system data (customers, asset information, GIS, etc.), hydraulic modeling calibration, review of preventive maintenance plans, review of reactive work orders, and review of risk-based asset management plan outcomes.

Recently, water utilities across North America are employing innovative technologies for monitoring the condition of some of their most critical assets. The Washington Suburban Sanitary Commission (WSSC) for example, was one of the early adopters of the Acoustic Fiber Optic (AFO) technology for the monitoring of PCCP transmission lines. Since 2007, WSSC has installed over 100 miles of AFO cabling and infrastructure for 145 miles of PCCP pipes, and it is claimed to be the longest continuous (near real-time) monitoring system in the USA. Based on WSSC estimates from 2021, the number of averted failures since 2010 are 44; which represents a noteworthy \$88 million in approximate savings (WSSC 2021).

This paper discusses the available condition monitoring systems used for urban drinking water assets, and broadly classifies these technologies based on the common area of knowledge and data gathering frequency. This paper has been developed based on the outcomes of the literature search conducted for the Water Research Foundation (WRF) research project 5191 entitled "Innovative Technologies to Improve Monitoring of Assets".

2. METHODOLOGY

As part of the work proposed for WRF 5191, a curated list of literature was developed from several research databases and other academic sources. Once the list of literature was determined to be closely related to condition monitoring of water assets, a database was developed and each document was classified based on a numbering system related to each area of knowledge, technology, and supporting topic.

The literature classification strategy employed the full downloadable Web of Science (WOS) database; which lists all the articles and their associated features, such as, author(s), publication year, title, keywords, times cited, etc. The features collected for each paper were automatically generated by the WOS database system and was the main data structure chosen for storing the literature for this research project.

The steps taken during the literature search process, and used to gather the relevant literature, developing the classifications, and further defining each monitoring technology, are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart of methodology

As indicated previously, each document was further classified based on the broad areas of knowledge. The result of this initial classification is shown in the Literature Review section of this paper.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

A comprehensive literature review has been conducted to identify the technologies, related topics and current state-of-the-art on condition monitoring for drinking water assets.

Various problem statements were first identified based on the conclusions of various industry reports, such as EPA (2023) and ASCE (2021), and the author’s experience in the field. The following are the problem statements.

- There is not enough funding to cope with the current drinking water asset renewal or replacement needs.
- Adoption of innovative monitoring technologies in municipalities is a slow, challenging, and complicated process.
- Innovative condition monitoring technologies need to anticipate sudden water asset failures and should reduce non-revenue water loss.
- Strategies must be developed to assist in the transition to new technologies and data-oriented asset management.

Further refinement of the problem statements to clearly identify the research needs required a strategic literature search that included a review of articles (journals, conferences, and magazines), white papers, reports, books, websites, standards, interviews, and other technical documents. Figure 2 shows a schematic of the literature search strategy employed.

Figure 2. Literature search strategy

An initial broad search for relevant literature returned 1,432 research articles. A word cloud on their abstracts suggested that most of the papers were related to the topic, since the words “wireless sensor networks”,

Figure 5. Broad classification of condition monitoring methods, technologies and topics

Due to the large number of equipment-based technologies and the overall broad classification initially used, an additional subclassification was considered relevant. The average data gathering frequency was used as the criteria for creating the following subgroups (also see Figure 5).

- a) Real-time or near-real-time monitoring:
 - i. In the business of integrated software and analytics platforms for monitoring of drinking water assets, there is a tendency is to define real-time monitoring, as the supply and transmission of at least one data point every 15 minutes for pressure sensors, or one data point per hour for metering devices.
- b) Periodic monitoring
 - i. Serves as a method to evaluate the condition of drinking water assets by inspecting or collecting data at predetermined longer intervals (i.e., daily, weekly, monthly, etc.).
- c) As-needed monitoring
 - i. Entails conducting relatively consistent asset inspections at unspecified time intervals, aligning more closely with reactive utility field operations, which typically involve inspections coupled with data collection. Assets that frequently require as-needed monitoring are typically designated by utilities as ‘problematic’.

The technologies mentioned in Figure 5 were classified based on the typical data gathering and transmission frequencies; however, some technologies have the capability to vary these frequencies based on the asset/utility needs (i.e., noise loggers).

5. INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES AND THE USE OF MACHINE LEARNING

The task of monitoring activities is certainly neither new, nor emerging in municipal drinking water systems. In fact, it is common practice in water utilities to perform periodical reading of meters, monitor the water quality of receiving waters, monitoring of water quality, and perform continuous measuring of water production.

The following section describes the emerging innovative technologies with a special focus on machine learning applications. These technologies are promising and valuable tools but may still require verification of practicality during installation and data gathering. Some of these technologies, although new to the drinking water sector, are well established and used in other industries, such as the oil and gas sector.

5.1 Innovative Technologies for Water Asset Condition Monitoring

In general, many of the condition monitoring technologies discussed in previous sections are relatively new, as most were developed or adapted in the early 2000s. However, there are emerging and trending technologies that

stand out as identified by the literature search. For instance, the use of vibration sensors that employ accelerometer data is one of the emerging equipment-based technologies. Additionally, there are other advancements related to additional or enhanced functionalities of equipment-based methods. For instance, certain flow traveling sensors, which were introduced over 15 years ago and employ hydrophones to detect leaks and gas pockets, are now being equipped with new capabilities. These enhancements include the ability to suspend the device in the middle of the pipe and integrate an array of other sensors such as magnetometers, accelerometers, gyroscopes, and pressure sensors. Other notable mentions of “equipment” based technologies is the introduction of leak detection by dogs, which has been used for many years in the oil and gas industry and is gaining recent attention by water utilities.

However, one of the most noteworthy advancements in monitoring technologies is the use of machine learning, either as a technology by itself or as an additional capability for existing technologies and sensors. This integration of machine learning models has been possible by the widespread availability and transferability of extensive datasets continuously being collected by sensors.

5.2 Use of Machine Learning for Water Asset Condition Monitoring

The concept of machine learning itself is not new. Some of its algorithms (i.e., linear regression) have been used for at least 200 years. In fact, the term “machine learning” was coined in 1962, by a computer scientist at IBM (IBM n.d.) while developing a predicting behavior for a computer-based checkers game. Nowadays, machine learning concepts and algorithms are part of a broader term called artificial intelligence. What is relatively new and gaining momentum, is the use of proven data analytics and machine learning models for predicting asset performance and determining strategies to deal with prioritizing asset maintenance (Allouche et al. 2020). These types of solutions are under the umbrella of what is known as Software-as-a-Service (SaaS).

For the most part, these systems use neural network classification algorithms such artificial neural networks (ANN), convolutional neural networks (CNN), and deep neural networks (DNN), (Abdelmageed et al. 2022). To a lesser degree, these systems also use algorithms like support vector machines (SVM) k-nearest neighbors (kNN) and ensemble techniques, such as boosting technique, bagging technique, combining two learners (CNN-SVM), and random forests (Abdelmageed et al. 2022; Yussif et al. 2023) (see Figure 6).

Figure 1. Common machine learning algorithms used for water asset condition monitoring

When multiple data sources are available and when proper data scrubbing is performed to standardize the different data sources, data analysts can gain insights on the condition of drinking water systems from using multi-sensor data analysis. In general, these SaaS platforms integrate data from SCADA (supervisory control and data acquisition) systems, network sensors (flow, pressure, level, meters, etc.), water treatment plants and pump station information; and analyze it in conjunction with drinking water network characteristics found in geographic information systems (GIS), asset management programs, billing information and hydraulic models (Allouche et al. 2020).

One of the most recent developments is the commercial application of machine learning algorithms to data produced by noise loggers. The predicting or classification algorithms explained previously are used for removing background noises from pure leak signal. These types of systems have been successful in reducing false alarms (Latif et al. 2022) commonly found in noise logger monitoring systems. These systems claim accuracies in the range of 80 to 97% for reducing false leak localization (Yussif et al. 2023). In a similar manner, condition monitoring data from fiber optic sensor systems (FOSS) can also be supplied with machine learning capabilities to filter out background noise from vehicles and other objects passing nearby the FOSS sensor (Allouche et al. 2020).

Researchers also employ controlled laboratory setups to mimic pipeline leakages of various degrees and locations. By doing this, they gather data and train machine learning algorithms to achieve higher leak detection accuracies for future implementation in real-life scenarios. Shukla & Piratla (2020) have experimented with improving the leakage identification of pipeline accelerometer sensors by converting vibration signals into scalograms and training CNN algorithms to predict a leak from the frequency of the vibration signal over time. In that study, a total of 9,000 images were used to train the model and achieved prediction accuracies of leak detection up to 94% for the same laboratory pipeline setup.

The use of algorithms for predicting when and why certain pipelines need renewal or repairs is another important application. Studies have employed data from water distribution systems, taken from computerized maintenance monitoring systems (CMMS) and GIS, to train neural models on where and why pipelines were renewed or rehabilitated. These models use asset features like pipe diameter, length, material, age, history of failures, loads on the pipe (i.e., proximity to transportation infrastructures), land use, soil properties, hydraulic characteristics, and history of renovation. The results obtained by these studies (Kaminski et al. 2017; Yazdekhasti et al. 2020) indicate that once trained, the models can successfully predict the need of pipeline renewal with an accuracy between 85% to 87% in certain cases.

Finally, researchers have identified novel and resourceful uses of machine learning that relate to the condition monitoring of water meters. Deep learning algorithms have been used for remotely reading water meters using automatic image recognition. Salomon et al. (2020) indicates that this type of technology assists in the monitoring of water meters that do not come pre-equipped with data transmission capabilities and prevents disposing perfectly functioning meters.

Table 1 summarizes some of the common machine learning uses established for water asset condition monitoring, provides a brief description and applications.

Table 1. Summary of some of the uses of machine learning for water asset condition monitoring

ML Use Cases	Description and Application
Data Integration and Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SaaS platforms that perform data scrubbing, data standardization, prediction and analysis. • Combine data from SCADA, GIS, network sensors, billing information, hydraulic models, and other sources.
Anomaly Detection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifies outliers or abnormalities in data from water asset sensors such as: noise loggers and fiber optic sensor systems (FOSS). • Aids in the reduction of false alarms and unnecessary emergency triggers by automatically removing data points that deviate significantly from the norm.
Supervised Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Used by researchers in controlled laboratory settings to generate labeled data on pipe leaks, breaks or other pipe conditions, which in turn serves as the ground truth for supervised learning. • The main purpose is to improve the accuracy of new equipment-based technologies by creating labeled data, or the accuracy of established technology by feeding the model with historical data.
Predictive Maintenance or Asset Health Prediction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are models that forecast when pipeline maintenance or renewal is likely to be needed, with the aim of reducing downtime, optimizing maintenance schedules, and improving overall operational efficiency.

ML Use Cases	Description and Application
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use historical data on pipeline attributes (e.g., diameter, material, age), environmental factors (e.g., proximity roads, land use, soil properties) pipeline design, hydraulics, and history of renewal or repairs.
Image Recognition or Computer Vision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Algorithms are trained to analyze and understand visual content from images or videos, for example from images of water meter registers. • Allows the collection of data from key sensors that cannot be equipped with digital data transmission, or that require large expenses on communications infrastructure.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the general literature search for the classification of monitoring technologies, the following were identified as the current research needs for emerging innovative technologies.

1. Challenges of actual implementation of sensors due to damage during installation and need for evaluating sensor redundancy (Barrias et al. 2016).
2. Verification of practicality and implementation of emerging real-time online monitoring solutions (Gupta & Kulat 2018).
3. Evaluation of false positives and false negatives of emerging monitoring solutions, which could be by the hundredths or thousands in real-life situations (Shukla & Piratla 2020; Yazdekhashti et al. 2017).

Additionally, because of the on-going investigation on the use of artificial intelligence for water asset condition monitoring, some uses of machine learning were identified.

1. As a stand-alone method for developing insights from a vast number of data sources, including pressure sensor data, consumer data, SCADA, etc.
2. As an add-on resource for already established sensors to enhance leak detection accuracies.
3. As a tool for learning from past renewal experiences based on various training vectors (pipeline features) to be used in forecasting the need of future pipeline renovations without the need of any monitoring equipment.
4. As an enhancing factor for verifying the accuracy of emerging monitoring technologies where little to nonreal-life implementation has been performed.
5. As an image recognition system for reading dials or analog sensors/meters and for performing other close monitoring of important assets.

Further review of available literature from technology providers and insights from municipalities will be included for the WRF 5191 research project. It is anticipated that these additional sources of information could add more technologies and capabilities to the ones classified already in this paper.

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